

Adsorption of Hydrogen on Manganese Borate

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Manganese borate, MnB_4O_7 , is not reduced by hydrogen up to 600°; beyond this temperature, the borate tends to decompose.

Large volumes of hydrogen are adsorbed on the borate. The adsorption has a positive temperature coefficient in the range of 200–600°. It is believed to be partly chemisorption and partly absorption into the lattice.

The reduction of a number of metal borates, such as those of copper, nickel, cobalt, and silver, had been studied in this laboratory before. With all these borates it was observed that the reduction generally followed the course:

although the temperature required for complete reduction was different for the different systems and in the case of cobalt borate, complete reduction could not be achieved. It was also observed that in addition to the reduction, an amount of hydrogen was adsorbed by the system. This also varied for the different borates; in the case of silver it was unusually high. The reducibility of the different borates by hydrogen also appears to be generally comparable to those of the corresponding oxides.

From free-energy considerations¹, manganese oxide should require much higher temperature for its reduction and from an analogy it is believed that manganese borate may not be reduced at temperatures even to 800°. No information is available in the literature on the properties of manganese borate, except the method of its preparation and its use as a drier². It has been found in the present investigation that manganese borate is not reducible by hydrogen even at 600° and beyond this temperature, the borate itself tends to decompose, but large quantities of hydrogen are adsorbed on the borate. The extent of adsorption has been studied at different temperatures and compared with the adsorption on manganese oxide. A probable mechanism of the nature of adsorption has been put forward.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Manganese Borate and Manganous Oxide.—Dry methods were not found convenient for synthesis of manganese borate because of the high temperatures required. In wet method great care regarding the concentration of the solutions and ex-

1. This Journal, 1962, 39, 333, et seq.

2. Proc. International Conf. on Peaceful Uses of Atomic Energy, 1956, vol. 8, 176.

3. "Encyclopedia of Chem. Tech.", 1958, Vol. 6, p. 738.

perimental conditions had to be taken in order to obtain a borate of definite composition.

Manganese borate was obtained by metathesis between molar solutions of AnalaR grade borax and of manganese sulphate in the cold. Constant stirring was necessary during precipitation. The product was filtered rapidly under suction. It was washed successively with 5% boric acid solution, ethanol, and distilled water. After drying for a few hours by suction, it was dried at 100° in an electric oven. Final dehydration of the borate was done at 500° for about 4 hours. The pale brown product conformed to the composition, MnB_4O_7 . (Found: B, 20.63, 20.56; Mn, 26.53, 26.61. Calc. for MnB_4O_7 : B, 20.59; Mn, 26.13%).

Manganous oxide was prepared by thermal decomposition *in vacuo* at 350° (for 2 hours) of crystalline manganese oxalate, $MnC_2O_4 \cdot 2H_2O$. Manganese oxalate was prepared by slow mixing of hot concentrated solutions of oxalic acid and potassium permanganate⁴.

Study of the Reaction.—The same apparatus as that described by Khundkar⁵ was used. A quantity of manganese borate was weighed into a platinum boat and placed in the reaction temperature zone in the closed system which had previously been evacuated and filled with pure hydrogen at atmospheric pressure. The decrease in gas volume at different intervals of time was noted and these volumes were then corrected to N. T. P. and plotted against time in Fig. 1. The water vapour formed was absorbed in P_2O_5 , taken in a small boat at the exit end of the reaction tube.

FIG. 1

4. *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1924, 16, 606.

5. *This Journal*, 1952, 29, 341.

The amounts of hydrogen consumed (corrected to N. T. P.) at different temperatures (200-600°) have been plotted in Fig. 1. In order to compare the results precisely, the same amounts of manganese borate (0.2 g.) were taken for each experiment. Extraction of the product of the reaction with pure anhydrous methanol showed that no free boric oxide was present and hence it was concluded that reduction of manganese borate to metallic manganese and boric oxide had not taken place and that the hydrogen uptake was due entirely to the adsorption by the borate itself. It was interesting to note that the borate changed colour from pale brown to light grey after the reaction. Adsorption of hydrogen without reduction, similar to that observed here, had been reported in the case of manganous oxide and other metallic oxides and mixed oxides⁶.

DISCUSSION

Extents of Adsorption at Different Temperatures

The extent of total uptake of hydrogen was relatively small (only 5.4 ml in 8 hrs.) at 200°. At this temperature there was a slight initial adsorption of less than 1 ml of hydrogen after which there was a long induction period lasting about 4 hours before further volume change took place.

At 300°, the adsorption took place steadily from the beginning for about 450 minutes, after which it stopped, the total amount of hydrogen taken up being 29.2 ml. The same trend of adsorption was followed at higher temperatures to 600°. In all cases there was an initial small but rapid uptake followed by a slower and almost linear change; the gas adsorption also became very slow (<1 ml/hr.) after about 7 or 8 hours and it was taken that equilibrium had been reached at this stage.

Experiments were also done with manganous oxide at 400° and 500°. The same amount (0.2 g.), as that used for experiments with manganese borate, was taken in this case. Before starting the experiments, a final reduction of manganous oxide *in situ* was done at 250° in presence of hydrogen for a short period. This was necessary because manganous oxide is easily oxidised to higher oxides in presence of air, even at room temperatures. After this, "degassing" was done for several hours to remove traces of hydrogen which might have been adsorbed during initial reduction. The uptake of hydrogen was found to take place slowly but regularly both at 400° and 500° and became immeasurably slow after 6 to 7 hours. Total uptake at 400° was 5.6 ml, but at 500° it was 5.4 ml.

Nature of Adsorption

It is probable that hydrogen taken up by manganous borate is due to "activated adsorption" as described by Taylor⁶ and is distinct from physical adsorption⁷. "Activated adsorption" is relatively a slow process, characterised by typical activation energy, and can be due to three causes:

6. Taylor and Williamson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 2168.

7. Taylor, *ibid.*, 1931, **53**, 578.

(i) It can be due to actual electron transfer on the surface and the process is usually termed chemisorption.

(ii) It can be due to diffusion of the gas into the interior of the substance. This process is called absorption.

(iii) It can be due to the reaction of the adsorbate with the impurities in the surface which might not have been completely removed by conventional "degassing" processes.

The last cause should not account for more than 1 to 2 ml of uptake.

As large amounts of gas were taken up, it was likely that absorption was also taking place with chemisorption. Absorption of gases is not unlikely on powdered surfaces, particularly at higher temperatures.

Chemisorption on manganese borate (as also on manganous oxide) may take place in either of the following ways :

(a) By adsorption of hydrogen on the metal ions, *i.e.*, the Mn^{2+} ions, containing an unfilled 'd' level.

(b) By adsorption of hydrogen on the oxygen ions and reacting to form hydroxyl ions. The process can be shown as:

In the case of manganese borate, it seems likely that adsorption of acidic gases, *e.g.*, H_2 and CO , would take place on oxygen ion sites. The increase of total adsorption with increase of temperature may be due, among other factors, to the increase in lattice "defect" concentration in manganese borate in such a way as to increase the adsorption. This view finds support from Taylor's observation of different adsorption activities on manganous oxide by differently prepared samples⁶.

Magnetic Evidence on Mechanism of Adsorption

During the process of adsorption of hydrogen on manganese borate (*vide supra*), the Mn^{2+} ions change to Mn^+ ions. These ions have the following electronic configurations:

Measurement of magnetic susceptibility of manganese borate after hydrogen adsorption could therefore provide useful information. After each experiment, a portion of the manganese borate containing adsorbed hydrogen was taken for magnetic susceptibility measurements in a Curie-Cheveneau balance. The results of the magnetic measurements are recorded in Table I together with data on the stock sample used in the experiments.

TABLE I

Temp.	H ₂ adsorbed.	$\chi_m \times 10^6$	No. of unpaired electrons.
	Stock sample	87.36	4.97
200°	5.4 ml	86.77	4.95
300°	20.2	88.33	5.02
400°	34.6	88.91	5.05
500°	45.5	89.95	5.10
600°	52.3	72.44	5.20
*400°	5.6	..	..
*500°	5.4	..	..

*Manganous oxide used.

It will be seen that the magnetic susceptibility value for the 200° reduction product is lower than that of the stock sample. After this the values show a steady increase above that of the stock sample.

If it is believed that hydrogen adsorption takes place on the oxygen ion sites (in the borate anion lattice) resulting in the formation of a hydroxyl ion and the release of an electron, the electron would then go to the '4s' level of manganese, thereby increasing the number of unpaired electrons from 5 to 6. This would be expected because of the fact that the half-filled 'd' level is relatively stable.

That 5 unpaired electrons exist in manganese borate can be seen from the following calculation (the same method of calculation was used to determine the number of unpaired electrons shown in Table I).

The magnetic moment μ_B in Bohr magnetons is given by the equation:

$$\mu_B = 2.83 \sqrt{\chi_m T}$$

where χ_m = molar susceptibility, T = temp. in °K. Putting χ_m (for stock sample) = 14158×10^{-6} and $T = 306.1^\circ\text{K}$, we have $\mu_B = 5.89$ Bohr magnetons. Using the approximate relationship:

$$\mu_B = \sqrt{n(n+2)}$$

where 'n' is the number of unpaired electrons, the value for which is found to be equal to 4.97 (which may be taken within experimental error as 5.00).

Table I shows that the number of unpaired electrons, as calculated from the magnetic susceptibility, reaches a maximum of 5.2. If hydrogen was only chemisorbed on the oxygen ions and subsequent reduction of all the Mn^{2+} ions to Mn^+ took place, the number of unpaired electrons would come to six. For the amount of manganese borate used (0.2 g.), this would require chemisorption of about 10 ml of hydrogen. Now, that the average number of unpaired electrons was raised to 5.2 only, chemisorption, according to the mechanism postulated, could account only for a relatively small part of the total gas uptake. The remainder of the gas taken up might have been through diffusion (absorption) into the "defect" lattice of manganese borate.

In our previous work with silver borate¹, it was observed that the hydrogen uptake had a negative temperature coefficient, whereas in the present case hydrogen uptake showed a positive temperature coefficient. It may be pointed out in this respect that the two systems studied are quite different from each other. In the case of silver borate, reduction to metallic silver took place followed by adsorption on the metal surface, but in the case of manganese borate, hydrogen was adsorbed on the borate itself without any reduction taking place. Benton *et al.*⁸ and Taylor⁹ observed maxima and minima in the isobars for hydrogen adsorption of nickel powder and mixed manganous-chromic oxides respectively. Beeck *et al.*⁹ thought that the low temperature process was both physical and non-activated chemical adsorption, and the high temperature process was absorption. According to Trapnell¹⁰, different processes probably predominate at different temperatures. It appears that many different types of systems will have to be studied before any generalisation could be made.

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8. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2325.

9. *Colloid Sci.*, 1948, 3, 505.

10. "Chemisorption", Butterworths Scientific Publications, 1955, p. 10.